

Orokaiva

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Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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Entry tags: Religion, Oceanic Religions

The Orokaiva consist of several tribes that reside in the Oro Province of Papua New Guinea. The Orokaiva have a history of European contact, as Papua New Guinea was annexed by the British government in 1888, and subsequently became an Australian territory in 1905. This entry focuses specifically on the Aiga tribe around the time of 1925, as the Aiga are at this point "less contaminated by European influence than most of the others" (Williams and Murray, 1930:7). This entry considers the Orokaiva religious group to be coterminous with the society at large; the religious sphere of Orokaiva life is bound up with the functioning of the society as a whole. The Orokaiva religion is concerned primarily with spirits of the dead. A Taro Cult was established in the early 1900's, and was originally directed toward supplicating taro spirits. This quickly shifted towards the placation of spirits of ancestors and departed relatives, who are said to control taro growth. The Orokaiva Taro Cult is both a fertility cult and cult of the dead. Religious practitioners (called taro men) act as medicine men, sorcerers, and weather magicians.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 1925 CE

Region: Northern Province, Papua New Guinea

Region tags: Oceania, Melanesia, Papua New Guinea

Northern Province, Papua New Guinea circa 1925

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Morrow, D.O. (Jul., 1970). Subsistence economy and supportive practices: Cross-cultural codes 1. *Ethnology*, 9(3), 302-330.
- Source 1: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 2: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 3: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oj23-001>

– Source 1 Description: Williams, F. E. (Francis E., & Murray, H. (1930). *Orokaiva Society*. London: Oxford University Press.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oj23-002>

– Source 2 Description: Williams, F. E. (Francis E. (1928). *Orokaiva Magic*. Papua. Government Anthropologist. Anthropology. Report. London: Oxford University Press, H. Milford.

– Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=oj23-000>

– Source 3 Description: Latham, C. S., & Beierle, J. (2004). *Culture Summary: Orokaiva*. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: With European occupation of Papua came European religious beliefs. However, this entry focuses on a particular location where European influence is limited, making it possible to study native beliefs. "Since the European occupation of Papua there have sprung up in various parts of the territory a number of new religious cults" (Williams, 1928:3). "The tribe with which I am best acquainted is that of the Aiga, who seemed to offer the best opportunities for research because they are fairly central and as yet less contaminated by European influence than most of the others" (Williams and Murray, 1930:7).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to occur constantly any time of the year (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating) indicates that external warfare seems to be absent or rare (original code 1). SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Orokaiva are inferred to be unpacified because warfare frequency is greater than or equal to 3. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: There is no process for assigning religious affiliation among the Orokaiva aside from being born into a particular clan.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: "The means of disseminating the Taro cult have already been discussed in general terms: we have seen that they are (a) contact transmission and (b) active proselytism" (Williams, 1928:31).

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Williams (1928:17-18) describes one instance of proselytizing, and indicates that it has not been very effective. It can thus be assumed that proselytizing is not mandated.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: Williams (1928:17-18) describes one instance of proselytizing, and indicates that it has not been very effective. It can thus be assumed that proselytizing is not mandated.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: "The other method of dissemination is by the active propaganda of the Taro men. This method, although it may attract more notice, has not exerted the same steady pressure as [contact transmission]" (Williams, 1928:17).

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Orokaiva religion has official political support in the sense that the religious and political spheres of life are not distinguished from one another.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1745 (Religio-political overlap) indicates that no formal political office is present among the Orokaiva [SCCS Variable 1740 coded as '10']. Source of information: Lang, 1988; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a formal religious or polity legal code.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1300

Notes: "Out of a total Orokaiva population of some 9,000, this tribe [the Aiga] numbers approximately 1,300, who are scattered in nearly fifty villages on or between the Opi and Kumusi rivers" (Williams and Murray, 1930:7).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "There are some who are recognized as leaders and who are very strongly 'possessed', and others who are little more than laymen. However, it is possible to include them all under the name of ba-embo, which means literally 'Taro man'. Such men, who, like the Baigona men, might be called priests of the cult, officiate and lead in the ceremonial feasting; they perform certain duties in the taro gardens; they make a special practice of jipari and similar contortions; and they subject themselves to certain taboos" (Williams, 1928:10).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scripture among the Orokaiva.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of monumental religious architecture.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Every human being survives death, and the entity which thus survives, whatever its form, is called a sovai" (Williams and Murray, 1930:260).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Notes: "I cannot, for instance, discover from my informants that the asisi is regarded as an entity separate from but residing in the body to which it belongs. It is not a 'breath of life', a vital principle, or an animating essence...the asisi is the native's name for a spiritual manifestation of anything; or for an immaterial self which co-exists with but is separable from the concrete self; or, in other words, whenever anything functions apart from its concrete self, it does so by means of a spiritual substitute which is called its asisi" (Williams and Murray, 1930:265).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Upon death, the human soul becomes a sovai, and will remain in his/her local village for some time. There are "a number of definite localities belonging (sentimentally if not actually) to the various clans, whither their people are supposed to repair after death. Such localities are called sovai-ta-na or 'sovai villages', and almost every one of the clans of the Aiga tribe could name its own. They take the form of some well-defined feature such as a hill, rock, or pool" (Williams and Murray, 1930:279-280).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: "The Orokaiva does not think of a happy home for the departed. It is true that at the graveside the sovai is bidden to go to some place of sunshine where there are neither march-flies nor mosquitoes to bother him, but there is no definite idea of where this place is nor of what manner of life the sovai may lead there; and the description as far as it goes does not seem to suit the tangible examples of sovai-ta-na which I have seen. There are one or two tales of sky-dwellers but no hint of a heaven (though there is the extremely vague belief that some sovai go aloft, and are accordingly known as i-sovai or 'upper' sovai. Among these are the diroga or spirits of those slain in fight. It was never suggested, by the way, that these i-sovai were in any sense superior to the others.) There is also an interesting tale of the underworld into which a man follows his deceased wife, and finds there a very large population of sovai, including some of his relatives. But this, as the native often says, is hihi—'only a fairy-tale'" (Williams and Murray, 1930:281).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "...one general doctrine seems common to all the Orokaiva: this is the doctrine of animal

reincarnation. After death a man's spirit reappears in the form of some creature—pig, snake, crocodile, cuscus, fire-fly, for example—which haunts the bush, and is regarded as dangerous and, on the whole, abominable, but which must not be offended" (Williams, 1928:25).

↳ In a human form:
– I don't know

↳ In animal/plant form:
– Yes

Notes: "...one general doctrine seems common to all the Orokaiva: this is the doctrine of animal reincarnation. After death a man's spirit reappears in the form of some creature—pig, snake, crocodile, cuscus, fire-fly, for example—which haunts the bush, and is regarded as dangerous and, on the whole, abominable, but which must not be offended" (Williams, 1928:25).

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation in the form of an inanimate object.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "...the body is wrapped in pandanus-leaf mats and bark-cloth for burial. The grave (use) is 3 or 4 feet deep. It contains an oblong 'coffin' (detemba), the floor of which is made of palm-wood strips like that of a house. The detemba is really no more than a strong framework of size sufficient to accommodate the body in a supine position. It is eventually covered with a roofing of poles and a large sheet of bark (gapa) to protect the corpse from the earth when it is thrown in" (Williams and Murray, 1930:213).

↳ Cremation:
– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:
– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:
– Yes

Notes: "...the body is wrapped in pandanus-leaf mats and bark-cloth for burial. The grave (use) is 3 or 4 feet deep. It contains an oblong 'coffin' (detemba), the floor of which is made of palm-wood strips like that of a house. The detemba is really no more than a strong framework of size

sufficient to accommodate the body in a supine position. It is eventually covered with a roofing of poles and a large sheet of bark (gapa) to protect the corpse from the earth when it is thrown in" (Williams and Murray, 1930:213).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: Williams and Murray, 1930:213

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: Williams and Murray, 1930:213

↳ Cannibalism:

– Yes

Notes: The Orokaiva would occasionally consume the flesh of captives. See Williams and Murray, 1930: 171-177 for more details.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices in burials.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: For a detailed description of Orokaiva burial practices, see questions below and Williams and Murray, 1930:210-215.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cenotaphs.

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: The deceased are buried in the bush outside of the village. This space is not described as a cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of family tomb-crypts.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: "Formerly the grave was under the house of the deceased; now by Government regulation it is in the bush at some distance from the village. It is natural that the natives should do their best to evade this regulation, because the custom of burial under the house is no doubt based on sentiment. Informants repeatedly state that they dislike burying their dead at a distance because they are sad or 'belly-sore'. I have also heard that they dislike the thought of a grave neglected and overgrown; but the principal idea is, as informants have stated it to be, that the living cannot bear the parting with the dead" (Williams and Murray, 1930:215).

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: In the bush outside of the village

Notes: "The grave is placed in the bush not far from the village, and a small house is built over it in which the widow secludes herself, just as in former times she would have been secluded over her husband's grave in her own house. When a Government patrol draws near, the grave shelter is of course empty" (Williams and Murray, 1930:215).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "...there is nothing to suggest a deity or any supernatural being of independent existence, least of all a high-god. I do not know of any cosmogony, and there is no attribution of divine powers to the phenomena of nature. On the whole it will be found that Orokaiva religion concerns itself primarily with the spirits of the dead" (Williams and Murray, 1930:168).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: "...there is nothing to suggest a deity or any supernatural being of independent existence, least of all a high-god. I do not know of any cosmogony, and there is no attribution of divine powers to the phenomena of nature. On the whole it will be found that Orokaiva religion concerns itself primarily with the spirits of the dead" (Williams and Murray, 1930:168).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Every human being survives death, and the entity which thus survives, whatever its form, is called a sovai" (Williams and Murray, 1930:260). "The word asisi, which is thus seen to be of very wide meaning, may stand not only for a manifestation of the living, but also for a manifestation of the dead, i.e. a ghost, visible or invisible. But it must be made clear that in proper usage asisi is not wholly synonymous with the being that survives death, viz. the sovai, though there is some confusion between the two words" (ibid. pg. 265).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "(1) The sovai is sometimes conceived of as immaterial but retaining human characteristics. (2) It is also conceived of as taking the concrete form of beast, bird, reptile, or fish. (3) It is also conceived of as a semi-human monster of altogether frightful disposition inhabiting the bush; or in this case it might be nearer the truth to say that there are imaginary monsters (fiends, hobgoblins) to whom the name sovai is extended, and who are thus identified with spirits of the dead. (4) Fourthly, there are a few instances in which the sovai are known by personal names and, apart from their constant appearance in legends, are thought of as still actually existing" (Williams and Murray, 1930:268).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: "All the things and processes of the world exist or happen per se; they are not under any omnipotent control nor do they submit to continual regulation by any personal powers. But we have also seen that they may be influenced for good or evil by the sovai, i.e. those beings who survive death" (Williams and Murray, 1930:288).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "But apart from the favours which the sovai are supposed to bestow on specialists, we find that every gardener and hunter feels that the dead may send him success. It is true that the negative side of this proposition is more often in evidence, i.e. he is more prone to attribute failure to the displeasure of the sovai than success to their favour, but there is, nevertheless, the belief that they are able to make the gardens flourish and to drive the pigs into the pig-nets, and this is proved by the custom of adjuring the sovai to do so in the farewell address at the grave" (Williams and Murray, 1930:283).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "But such benevolent conduct on the part of the sovai is to say the least unusual, and it must be confessed that on the whole the Orokaiva regards his relatives and friends after their death as enemies. Any failure of the crops may be attributed to them; they may baffle the hunters; they may send the pigs to break through the fences and despoil the gardens. Sickness is perhaps ascribed more often to the malevolence of sovai than to any other cause" (Williams and Murray, 1930:283). "The native goes in real fear of his dead relatives and in perpetual anxiety lest he should offend them and incur their displeasure. This is probably the reason why a dead man's garden is taboo to his relatives: they fear he may infect the products of it out of sheer malice" (Williams, 1928:58).

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The sovai are given offerings of food (Williams and Murray, 1930:285), so presumably, the sovai possess hunger.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: "...there is nothing to suggest a deity or any supernatural being of independent existence, least of all a high-god. I do not know of any cosmogony, and there is no attribution of divine powers to the phenomena of nature. On the whole it will be found that Orokaiva religion concerns itself primarily with the spirits of the dead" (Williams and Murray, 1930:168).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: "...there is nothing to suggest a deity or any supernatural being of independent existence, least of all a high-god. I do not know of any cosmogony, and there is no attribution of divine powers to the phenomena of nature. On the whole it will be found that Orokaiva religion concerns itself primarily with the spirits of the dead" (Williams and Murray, 1930:168).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: "It is clear that the sanctions of Orokaiva morality are something less solid than legal authority, and that there are virtually no guardians of the law. We may look for a supernatural guardian, i.e. for a supernatural sanction; but except within a limited field of conduct we should look in vain. By the supernatural sanction I mean the desire to please or the fear of offending any of those occult beings which are felt to possess more than human powers; and in Orokaiva religion, as we have seen, such beings are first and foremost, indeed almost exclusively, identified with the spirits of the dead, of

whom the living stand in very real fear. The supernatural sanction, however, may be very briefly dismissed, for except in relation to semi-religious observances it cannot be said to exercise much influence. Though if we allowed a place in our list of native virtues to filial piety, even limited to piety of the posthumous kind, we should be dealing with what is truly one of the most important obligations in native conduct and one which is to a great extent dependent on the supernatural sanction. But this hardly comes within the scope of our present subject" (Williams and Murray, 1930:327).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: (Williams and Murray, 1930:327)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic evidence.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "There are first the norms, the ideals, the theoretical standards of morality...These standards define the kinds of behaviour which, in relation to the society which has evolved them, are satisfactory, i.e. the kinds of behaviour which have been found to work. Selected by generations, they have been unconsciously designed to suit the narrow needs of family, clan, or tribal unit; they are essentially social norms, and they are meant to ensure the smooth running and happiness of social life" (Williams and Murray, 1930:308).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For a detailed description of Orokaiva values, see Williams and Murray, 1930:315-321.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: See Williams and Murray, 1930:316

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: "A passive virtue, yet one which possibly ranks first in Orokaiva estimation, is that of good temper. I find no specific term for it, but the good-tempered man is called simply javo-embo, or 'good man'. A squabbler, a vituperator, or a bully is strongly disliked..." (Williams and Murray, 1930:319). "Another ideal is that of courtesy, and by this I mean something wider than mere politeness" (ibid, pg.320).

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: "This willingness to co-operate or assist is a sufficiently striking native trait which we may call simply helpfulness" (Williams and Murray, 1930:318).

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Industriousness

Notes: See Williams and Murray, 1930:317

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Although participation does not appear to be mandatory, the Orokaiva have occasional festivals associated with the Taro cult. "The Taro Cult began about 1915 and soon evolved into ritual practices meant to placate the spirits of the dea (SOVAI) who control the taro crop. Thus, it is both a fertility cult and a cult of the dead. Taro men lead the ritual which includes choral singing, drumming, feasting, and violent shaking movements" (Latham, and Beierle, 2004). For more detailed information on the Taro cult, see Williams, 1928:7-11, 37-48.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: "Whatever the difficulty of deciding between these two, however, there can be no doubt that both of them, family and clan, mean more to the individual than does the tribe or the somewhat loose confederacy of clans within the tribe" (Williams, Francis, & Murray, 1930:107). The Orokaiva do not have a political authority beyond the community, which is reflective of autonomous bands and villages (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent) indicates that the Orokaiva have patrilineal descent with clan-communities. Additionally, the Orokaiva live in segmented communities, with patrilineal sibs. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22. Because the Orokaiva have kin ties, they are most accurately described as a tribe.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: "A native's education consists in the gradual and effortless assimilation of the customs and manners of his people; and there is no school save that of daily contact with his elders, whose example is merely the reproduction of a previous example set to them" (Williams and Murray, 1930:324).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: "Political organization incorporates no central authority or hereditary leadership. Instead, it is characterized by big-men(EMBO DAMBO) and an ascendancy of elders who have proved themselves equal to the task. Such men command the respect of the village, based upon observed qualities of generosity, diligence, wealth, ability to make wise decisions, and skill in arranging ceremonial activities. This status confers no sanctioning authority, however. The Orokaiva tribes, around twelve in number, are very loose units politically and recognize no single leader" (Latham and Beierle, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: "Land transport is done exclusively by human carriers, with at most the aid of a tumpline, a carrying pole, or the like...Routes of land transport consist exclusively (or almost so) of unimproved trails or footpaths" (Column 7, Land Transport, from Murdock and Morrow, 1970). From this information, it can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 10, Police) "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery." [Note: identical to SCCS Variable 90].

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 9, Judiciary), "supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community." [Note: Identical to SCCS Variable 89].

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: "But how are these [criminal and civil] offences prevented, or how punished? It will be understood that there is no such thing as a central authority to enforce the law. Orokaiva chieftainship (to risk the use of the word) is of the most elementary kind, and certainly involves no power of inflicting punishment, nor even any means of maintaining order except by the exercise of purely personal influence" (Williams and Murray, 1930:325).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a formal legal code.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 149, Writing and Records, indicates that writing and records are absent among the Orokaiva (Murdock and Provost, 1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Orokaiva rely predominantly on agriculture and fishing for subsistence. Animal husbandry, hunting, and gathering provide supplementary food sources. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Orokaiva rely predominantly on agriculture and fishing for subsistence. Animal husbandry, hunting, and gathering provide supplementary food sources. Source of information

from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.